

BfR assesses analyses of substances with hormone-like activity in natural mineral waters

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The presence of substances with hormone-like activity in natural mineral waters has been repeatedly studied over the past few years. In a research project of the chemical and veterinary inspection agency (CVUA) Stuttgart, the potential oestrogen-like activity of natural mineral waters was analysed. Additionally, mineral waters were tested for substances that may exhibit oestrogen-like activity. It was also tested whether this activity is related to packaging in glass or plastic bottles.

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has assessed the hormone-like activity as well as the toxic effects of substances found in natural mineral waters. Oestrogen-like activities were not detected in these mineral waters, nor were concentrations of substances detected that could cause such activity. However, a number of substances were identified for which no data on hormone-like activity is available yet.

BfR concludes that mineral water should not exhibit hormone-like activity. BfR advises systematic step-by-step controls: Water obtained directly at the spring, water that has undergone treatment by bottlers and water that is available in shops, bottled mineral water of different storage periods should be analysed and compared. Additional research would be needed in order to assess a potential health risk.

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/bfr_bewertet_untersuchungen_zu_hormonaehnlichen_wirkungen_von_in_natuerlichen_mineralwaessern_vorkommenden_substanzen.pdf